

Quantum $\hbar/p = \Delta x$ from Action-Reaction Based on a Rest Co-ordinate System?

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In free particle quantum mechanics, $p = \hbar/\lambda$ and this leads to 2-slit interference if the slits are about a wavelength apart. This may give the sense of p creating the wavelength in space, but we argue here that the idea of wavelength is directly linked to an interaction and so the emergence of a Δx seems to be linked to a kind of action-reaction of the interaction and not the motion of the particle with rest mass and p . We make this argument on the basis of a particle with momentum p approaching a two slit apparatus which is moving with a constant velocity. In such a case, it is the overall interaction which defines the required slit separation and not simply p of the particle. As a result, a $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ is really associated with the overall interaction even though one may Lorentz transform into the rest frame of the moving 2-slit apparatus. We compare these ideas to the case of a photon.

Photon Scenario

A photon is known to undergo 2-slit interference if slit separation is about a wavelength apart, where:

$$\text{Time period} = \hbar/E \quad \text{and} \quad \text{wavelength} = \hbar/p \quad ((1))$$

Originally (in the early 1800s) a photon was thought to be a wave because of 2-slit interference. The equation for a wave is:

$$\text{Velocity} = c = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength} \quad ((2))$$

Later, Maxwell showed that a photon's electric and magnetic fields could be written in terms of:

$$\cos(-\omega t + kx) \quad ((3))$$

The electric and magnetic fields, however, define energy and momentum density and so one may show that:

$$E = \hbar \omega \quad \text{and} \quad p = \hbar k \quad ((3))$$

Then, given $x/t=c$ in all frames: $E = pc$ in all frames ((4))

$$((4)) \text{ is an equation of special relativity for } m_0=0, \text{ i.e. } E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((5))$$

We suggest that there are two key issues here. The first is that the photon moves at a speed of c and ((4)) suggests that:

$$\Delta t_1 = \text{constant}/E \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta x_1 = \text{constant}/p \quad ((6))$$

In other words, E and p are associated with motional increments Δt_1 and Δx_1 . At the same time, a photon is a self-wave with electric and magnetic fields creating an action-reaction motion which also involves the same intervals described in ((6)). A photon does not have rest mass and has no center-of-mass, so we suggest that the key idea is that the intervals ((6)) are linked with interaction and action-reaction. Furthermore, the photon in ((6)) is not interacting, but moving through space. For the interaction intervals of ((6)) to make sense, we suggest that an interaction must occur with a 2-slit apparatus at rest, i.e. one providing a set of rest co-ordinate axes.

One may consider a second frame moving at a speed $-v$ to the first one. In this frame, the photon with p has p' and so if one has a 2-slit system at rest, it must have:

Slit widths of the order: \hbar/p' and not \hbar/p ((7))

In the scenario above, however, the 2-slit apparatus is also moving and so there will be momentum from not only the photon, but the 2-slit apparatus. One must consider the overall interaction which involves both the photon and moving 2-slit apparatus momentum and so we argue that \hbar/p' is no longer the relevant slit separation. To find this value, one may go into the rest frame of the 2-slit apparatus to see that the result is \hbar/p as expected. In other words, it is the overall interaction which creates an overall p which is related to a Δx . Thus, Δx is an interaction length not a dynamical one. A photon moves with c , but if the 2-slit is also moving, there are two velocities c and v and an overall relative $c+v$. Thus, one does not have the usual \hbar/p linked to c motion because there are two p values in the picture. We suggest that the moving 2-slit apparatus may give some insight into why Δx is not a dynamical concept, but rather an interaction one.

This seems to lead to an issue with relating quantum mechanics to special relativity. In the case of a photon:

$$E=pc \rightarrow -Et+px=0 \quad ((8))$$

Special relativity can deal with dynamics as in the case of a speed c or v and x and t are dynamical variables. E and p , on the other hand, are interaction variables. The case of the photon shows that these mix. We have argued in previous notes that one may obtain special relativity only using interactional considerations about E and p . In particular, we argued that given $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $p = mv$ in nonrelativistic Newtonian mechanics, an acceleration of inertia m_0 may increase this inertia when it moves to $E = m(v) D$ ($D = \text{constant}$) such that $p = m(v)v$. In this view, there is only m_0 , E and p and no x and t appear although c and v are present. In particular, in (1) we explicitly argue that one may obtain $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ directly from E, p, v, c considerations with no spacetime present. Indirectly, however, spacetime must be present if one considers frames differing by a speed $-v$. Velocity by definition is dynamical.

This approach may be shown to yield a photon result for m_0 from:

$$EE = ppcc + m_0 m_0 c^4 \text{ with } m_0 \rightarrow 0 \quad ((9))$$

This then begs the question as to why one should consider any Δx or Δt to exist which leads to 2-slit interference (which is experimentally observable). We note that for a photon, $E=pc$ is of the form $\Delta x = c \Delta t$, thus in the photon case there is a direct link to space time and so there may be fixed intervals $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$, but these are based on measurements in a frame with a fixed origin. Thus, there could be a 2-slit interference experiment if the 2-slit apparatus is at rest.

The arguments above regarding a 2-slit which moves, however, show that $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ is not a dynamical, but an interactional length, perhaps linked to some overall action-interaction of the interacting photon and the moving 2-slit which now has momentum. Thus, even though $\hbar/p = \Delta x$ is dynamical for a photon relative to a rest 2-slit, this does describe the situation when the 2-slit apparatus is moving at constant speed. Overall momentum is the key and Δx is linked to this, suggesting that Δx is an interactional result.

The question then becomes: What happens for a particle with rest mass. The fact that it does not satisfy $E=pc$ seems irrelevant because if E and p are linked to action-reaction lengths in an interaction, so $E=pc$ simply shows that for the photon case, they also represent intervals which yield the velocity. In the moving rest mass they do not, but if E and p are linked to action-reaction lengths and times for a photon, then there is no reason that they could not also be so linked for a particle with rest mass.

This seems to imply that the argument that sets E and p linked to Δt and Δx through $E=pc$ is not correct because the quantum Δt and Δx are not dynamical values, but interactional, but in the photon case the two coincide, so using $E=pc$ to suggest E and p are linked to intervals may be fine. One has to realize, however, that it is an interaction and action-reaction which are associated with these Δt and Δx values as seen by the moving 2-slit apparatus example.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ is really associated with an interaction and so this length should not be considered dynamical, but interactional. In other words, it is a length linked to some kind of action-reaction. In the case of a photon, one has the special case of $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ being both dynamical ($E=pc$) and interactional (2-slit interference). We argue that the key idea is the interactional one because if one has a photon with momentum p such that the slits (of an apparatus at rest) should be \hbar/p apart, if the 2-slit apparatus moves at constant speed, then p relative to the 2-slit apparatus is different and one has interference based on this relative p value and not p measured in a frame in which the 2-slit apparatus moves. Thus, it is the overall p interaction which is key in ascertaining Δx and so we argue that Δx is not a dynamical length, but one associated with some kind of action interaction. Thus, there are two lengths and Δt in a problem. A particle may move with Δx and Δt intervals linked with speed, but there may be $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ for a particle with rest mass which have nothing to do with motion, but are linked strictly with action-interaction with a 2-slit apparatus at rest. Given that action-reaction seems to be a property linked with E and p , if one has $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ for a photon, one might suggest these two values apply to a particle with rest mass as E and p should be universal concepts. In Newtonian mechanics, interactions occur in a $dx \rightarrow 0$, so there is no notion

of action-reaction lengths, but the photon seems to show that they exist and so do so also for particles with rest mass, as 2-slit interference experiments confirm.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Newtonian Mechanics as the Driver of Special Relativity? Part 2 (preprint, zenodo, 2025)